

Deliverable interim report on project B5-1 Food and drink manufacturing: Establishing baseline contributions to climate change and identifying scope for Reduction of Environmental impACTs (REACT).

WP 2: Estimation of impacts from processing pathways

Deliverable 2.1.2: Animal feed interim report

for the Project B5-1 Food and drink manufacturing: Establishing baseline contributions to climate change and identifying scope for Reduction of Environmental impACTs (REACT).

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Summary

Distillery co-products have traditionally featured heavily in ingredients in UK based livestock feed production. However, recent interests in diverting the distillery coproducts towards anaerobic digestion for energy production have greatly reduced this linkage between the industries, encouraging instead a greater dependency on imported grains such as soyabean which come with a high environmental cost.

This work package aimed to explore the environmental impacts associated with animal feed production in Scotland and the ramifications of imported grain versus use of distillery co-products. In order to do this, data was drawn from literature and directly from industry to identify a basic ingredient list, and ingredient pathways in order to develop an LCA model. Five major ingredient pathways were highlighted: a) nationally produced crops; b) imported crops or crop-based product; c) co-product from other national industry; d) a simple processed non-crop additive; e) complex multi-ingredient additives. By working closely with RESAS project C2-1, national production data was developed for relevant Scottish crops (e.g. barley, wheat) and to feed into models for the co-products production such as spent grain from distilleries. In addition, the major countries of origin for the main imported crop and crop-based products were identified. These were found to be soyabean and sunflower seed, which are imported predominantly from Argentina and Sweden respectively. A suitable database has also been identified to use going forward (GFLI) for secondary data to support further model development.

Work is ongoing with industry to source full data to finish refining the model and to run it for a Scotland specific livestock feed creation scenario. In the interim, data has been provided by the industry on their in-house carbon footprint calculations. These have shown a potential difference in CF between mixes intended for different purpose (calf rearer feed versus feed aimed at dairy cows), but regardless of feed mix it showed clearly that the footprint associated with production itself was minor (only 2-3%) in comparison to the production and transport of the ingredients. This argues for the model to focus predominantly on accurately modelling the ingredients and alternatives to determine the most accurate CF and potential methods of mitigation.

Key Messages

- Calculations from industry show the processing aspect of animal feed production to be relatively low, with ingredient production and sourcing shown to dominate their estimations instead.
- The UK has an import dependency on high protein grain such as soyabean.
- This issue is exacerbated as distilleries increasingly are choosing to use their spent grain co-products for bio-energy production rather than diverting it into animal feed production.

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Introduction

The purpose of this interim report is to outline the system boundaries, and major inputs and outputs of an LCA model exploring animal feed production in Scotland. This work package (B5-1, WP 2) aims to estimate the impacts associated with crop and seafood processing pathways in Scotland. This will be done by combining industry data with data from literature to construct modelled scenarios for processing pathways in Scotland.

This deliverable (**D2.1.1**) is intended to provide the basic structure for the model exploring animal feed processing in Scotland. This has been informed by drawing details from literature and by engaging with the animal feed sector directly. It will be expanded on in Y3 (**D.2.1.3**) as real data is obtained from industry to process in the model to create a footprint for animal feed production in Scotland and the chance to explore improvements and linkages to other sectors.

Background

The food and drink sector are important both from a perspective of Scotland's economy, bringing in approximately 25 billion pounds to the UK (Food and Drink Federation, 2023) and its culture, however food and drink production are also a major source of anthropogenic GHG emissions. Worldwide, this represents 21-37% (IPCC, 2019), with 7.6Mt CO₂ estimated in 2017 at the Scottish level, 75% of which was attributed to livestock production (Lampkin *et al.*, 2019). But with national commitments to meet net zero by 2045, (Scottish Government, 2019) there is growing pressure to revolutionise our food system to move towards climate-smart and sustainable production and manufacturing options.

The high emissions from livestock are often attributed to three major aspects – the methane produced by ruminant animals, the associated emissions caused by animal feed production and manure production (Sykes *et al.*, 2019). Livestock feed itself can show a range in terms of CF and included ingredients, with the UK as a whole having a dependency on imported high protein grains, defined as containing 30-50% protein (FEFAC, 2021) for use in animal feed (with deficiency estimated at around 70% FEFAC, 2021; Rivington *et al.*, 2021). In 2021, these imports were estimated to be over £2.6 billion (Bedford, 2023).

Distillery co-products have traditionally featured heavily in ingredients in UK based livestock feed production (Zero Waste Scotland, 2015; Bell, 2019). However recent interests in diverting the distillery coproducts towards anaerobic digestion for energy production have greatly reduced this linkage between the industries, encouraging instead a greater dependency on imported grains such as soyabean (Chatham House, 2020) which are associated with higher carbon footprints (Duffy *et al.*, 2023).

It is the intention of this work package to work closely with projects C2-1 and later B1-6 to allow for work synergies to be realised and a detailed overview of Scottish food and drink production to be explored together.

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Methods

Literature was reviewed on the topic of the environmental impacts of livestock feed by means of LCA. This was used to establish a general overview of a typical animal feed production system, appropriate system boundaries and specific pathways for ingredient types (nationally produced crops, imported crops or crop-based product, co-product from other national industry, simple non-plant based additive and complex multi-ingredient additives). This was then used to inform the foundations of feed model creation.

Industry was engaged for the next step, obtaining in more detail the system and processing steps. Preliminary data was provided from industry for an example ingredient list and within house GHG estimations associated with each type. The pre and post processing carbon footprints were also provided for three example mixes (two for calf rearer and one for dairy feed), to allow for the exploration of processing footprint. The ingredient list provided was categorised by ingredient pathway as per the model, utilising import/export data produced in C2-1 where appropriate to identify which are likely to be imported and which are likely to be from national production (Table 1) with sunflower products covered under the umbrella of oilseeds.

For ingredients identified as imported crops or crop based product, a processing database produced in C2-1 WP 5 (Sandison, 2023a) was consulted to identify the major import pathways for each relevant crop, to allow for incorporation into the animal feed production model being constructed.

Table 1: Import and export data for selected crops from the UK. Adapted from Sandison (2023b)

Commodity	Export	Import	Nett	Overall Importer or exporter?
Barley	764,263	89,108	675,155	Exporter
Soyabean	72,128	3,077,322	-3,005,194	Importer
Durum Wheat	18,289	63,726	-45,437	Importer
Oats	133,039	25,172	107,867	Exporter
Wheat	492,809	1,930,070	-1,437,261	Importer
Legumes	262,648	32,741	229,907	Exporter
Oilseeds	293,421	2,809,876	-2,516,455	Importer

Results

The system boundaries and ingredient pathways for animal feed production was constructed from reference to literature and discussion with industry (Figure 1). Five ingredient pathways were identified: a) nationally produced crops, b) imported crops or crop-based product, c) co-product from other national industry, d) a simple processed non-crop additive and e) complex multi-ingredient additives. Though considered discrete pathways for each, some do interlink, with pathway a naturally feeding into pathway c. It is the ultimate intention for the model to address all stages of this diagram, though initial focus has been on the identified ingredient pathways.

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Figure 1: System boundaries for animal feed production where dark grey indicates system pathway for imported products, orange indicates system pathway for crops produced in Scotland, green indicates system pathway for co-products obtained from other Scottish industries, yellow indicates system pathway for non-crop based simple feed additives and light grey for system pathways for complex multi-ingredient feed additives. Arrows represent direction of output flow.

Using preliminary data from industry, feed ingredients were identified and categorised in terms of ingredient pathway for the sake of future modelling. This was then combined with industry in house calculations for later comparison with modelled output, as well as notes on method for model inclusion. Where possible data is taken from this project, or associated projects (C2-1, B5-1), in the absence of this data is intended to be drawn from GFLI database which has been identified as the most appropriate database for background processes and information, being a global animal feed production specific resource (GFLI, 2024). For complicated multi-ingredient additives, manufacturer data is used (provided by industry). In all cases information from literature would be used as required to fill in gaps in knowledge or augment existing information. This is summarised in Table 2.

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Table 2: Simplified list of raw materials included in feed production provided by industry, including industry calculations for carbon footprint (CF) for one tonne of ingredient and identified system pathway. Where A = nationally produced crops, B = imported crops or crop-based product, C = co-product from other national industry, D = a simple processed non-crop additive and E = complex multi-ingredient additives. Complex multi-ingredient additives have been anonymised at this stage to maintain industry confidentiality.

Raw Material	CF (kg CO₂e/t of Raw Material) estimated by industry	Description	Intended information source for model inclusion	System pathway
Barley	421.4	Crop	Utilising data from project C2-1 WP 5	A
Wheat	406.4	Crop	Utilising data from project C2-1 WP 6	A
Wheat Dark Grains	858.1	By product of the distilling industry	Construct estimate from literature/ this study	C
Malt Residuals	1321.7	Co-product from malting industry	Construct estimate from literature/ this study	C
Extracted Rapeseed Meal	722.9	Byproduct of rapeseed oil	Construct from data from GFLI database/literature	C
Sugar Beet Pulp	504.9	Residue from beat sugar industry	Construct from data from GFLI database/literature	C
Wheatfeed	294.5	Byproduct of flour industry	Construct from data from GFLI database/literature	C
Sunflower Lo-Pro	451.8	Sunflower seed meal (biprodut of sunflower oil)	Construct from data from GFLI database/literature	B
Oat Bran	401.4	Co-product of oatmeal	Construct from data from GFLI database/literature	B
Soya Hulls	971.3	Byproduct of soyabean processing	Construct from data from GFLI database/literature	B
Novapro	671.3	Rapeseed product, enhanced for rumens to make more effective	Direct data from GFLI database/literature	C
Salt Premix	145.9	Salt additive	Direct data from GFLI database/literature	D
Salmon Oil	934.6	Fish oil	Construct estimate from literature/ this study	D

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Limestone	97.1	Calcium additive	Direct data from GFLI database/literature	D
Vit E 50%	1387	Vitamin E additive	Direct data from GFLI database/literature	D
Ammonium Chloride	1086	Chemical additive to reduce milk fever and renal calculi	Direct data from GFLI database/literature	D
Complex additive 1	367.8	Protein mineral supplement	As reported by manufacturer	E
Complex additive 2	5482.7	Blend of vitamins, minerals, supplements and other nutritional additives	As reported by manufacturer	E
Complex additive 3	1086	Mixed feed additive	As reported by manufacturer	E
Complex additive 4	1086	Mixed feed additive	As reported by manufacturer	E
Complex additive 5	4183.2	Fatty acid additive to increase milk yield and fertility	As reported by manufacturer	E
Complex additive 6	1415	Calcium and magnesium additive	As reported by manufacturer	E
Complex additive 7	1219	Enzyme additive	As reported by manufacturer	E
Complex additive 8	5587	Selenium yeast additive	As reported by manufacturer	E
Complex additive 9	5587	Yeast culture to increase feed efficiency and cattle PH	As reported by manufacturer	E
Complex additive 10	5587	Vitamin supplement	As reported by manufacturer	E
Complex additive 11	5587	Natural feed additive that reduces methane	As reported by manufacturer	E

Referring to Table 1, two products were identified as imported crops, sunflower products and soyabean products. Referencing a UK import/export database produced in project C2-1 (Sandison, 2023a) the following details were obtained for quantity of imports per country in tonnes. Table 3 summarises the details for the top 4 importers for each, with all other countries of import showing less than 10% of the imports, and in many cases <1%. For Sunflower products, the top four countries accounted for 65% of all imports for Sunflower products, and 82% if all soya products.

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Table 3: Top countries of import for sunflower and soyabean products in 2020-2021 (Sandison, 2023a)

Sunflower products			Soya products		
Country of origin	Quantity in tonnes	% of total import	Country of origin	Quantity in tonnes	% of total import
Sweden	249,006	25	Argentina	1123118	36
Lithuania	156,954	16	Brazil	628918	20
UAE	137,373	14	Netherlands	501975	16
France	95,308	10	USA	257779	8

Industry provided the carbon footprint details of three example feed mixes, two that were blended for calf rearing, and one which was blended for feed for dairy cows. In the three examples, the two calf rearer blends showed a higher footprint than the dairy feed mix and were similar (0.03 difference prior to processing), suggesting that this may be a trend in feed production in general, but with so few comparisons no firm conclusions can be drawn on that matter. What can clearly be seen however, is that in all three cases processing only accounts for 0.02 kg CO₂ e, (2-3% as shown in the hotspot analysis Figure 2).

Table 4: Carbon footprint (CF) of example feed mixes from industry both pre and post processing, inclusive of transport.

Name	Type	Total CF (kg CO ₂ e/kg) Before processing	Total CF (kg CO ₂ e/kg) Finished Feed Delivered to Farm
Example Mix 1	Calf rearer	0.767472	0.78515
Example Mix 2	Dairy mix	0.618617	0.638596
Example Mix 3	Calf rearer	0.740457	0.760436

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Figure 2: Hotspot analysis exploring importance of processing impacts in feed production utilising data from industry for three example mixes.

Discussion and model building

Processing overview

Based on the industry data provided, the processing aspect of animal feed production has a relatively minor contribution to the overall carbon footprint of livestock feed (2-3%) whereas the rest can be attributed to the production and transport of feed ingredients. Lacking transparency, the industry provided data does not give enough data resolution to draw conclusions beyond that as to which aspects are covered and are hotspots themselves in the ingredient production and transport, but nonetheless their contribution overall is marked (97-98% of industry provided CFs). Though the data provided does include a soyabean product (soya hulls), it does not include soya meal or other higher value soya products, making a comparison at this stage difficult. Anecdotal evidence has indicated this has been a deliberate ethical choice by the manufacturers to avoid use of soy products where possible. However soya meal and other products are also often included in animal feed production (Barker, 2023; Duffy *et al.*, 2023), and as literature have reported figures as high as 29.47kg CO₂ e per kg of soyabean produced or 29,470 kg CO₂ e per tonne (Escobar *et al.*, 2020), this could have a substantial effect on the end result. A such these should also be factored into the modelling to allow for better comparison of soya-based products versus alternatives.

With ingredients highlighted as the main contributor to the CF of animal feed at this stage, it argues for focusing on this aspect when building the future model to allow for better exploration of causes of GHG emissions and ways to mitigate them. This is further discussed in the subsequent sections. The identified ingredient pathways are also relevant for the second stage of this section of the project, with the development of this aspect of the model also directly feeding into the later production of a whisky processing model.

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Crop production

National crop production is also in the process of being modelled in close conjunction with C2-1, with particular focus on barley and wheat. Utilising data from a long-standing experiment run by the James Hutton Institute, the environmental impacts of conventionally grown crops in Scotland are being calculated, with further investigation into integrated farming practices represented in the study also intended to be included in the joint assessments of C2-1 and this research. This data will then be used in this project to feed directly into the modelled co-product creation aspects, as well as both as a comparison against imported products and as a standalone ingredient in the livestock feed production itself.

Imported goods

Soyabean products and sunflower products have been identified as key imported ingredients for Scottish production of animal feed, with soya-based feed use in particular showing an increase of 8% since 2012 (Chatham House, 2020). Though others might be identified and included as research continues, these will be the focus of the next stage of this study. Working closely with Project C2-1, key import pathways and countries of origin have been identified, with modelling started to explore these impacts. Considerations of land use change are intended to also be explored given the connection between key countries of import, with Argentina showing as the area supplying the most soya products to the UK (Table 3) but also the country showing the second greatest loss of tree cover, largely due to agricultural demands (Chatham House, 2020; Gibbs, 2020).

Distillery co-products

Traditionally the use of co-products from industries like whisky have played a distinct role in animal feed, both via unprocessed fresh feed and as a further processed component of commercial livestock feed such as pot ale syrup (PAS) and dried distillers grains with solubles (DDGS) (Zero Waste Scotland, 2015; Bell, 2019). Distillery products are estimated to have a range of 27-36% protein content marking them as mid-high protein sources (Bell, 2019).

Recently new uses for the distillery co-products such as bio-energy production have challenged this interconnection between industries. With only 10 facilities in Scotland still producing PAS (White, 2020) and with co-products going into animal feed reduced by 57% (Bell, 2019) there is increasing pressure on imported high protein grain to fill the gap. Though there is a potential conflict noted for the distilleries and for national energy production interests, Duffy *et al.* (2023) found that use of co-products in animal feed had a more significant impact on GHG emissions than diversion into bioenergy, with 2.5-8 times more offset being seen by the former.

Co-products will be modelled using data from the Scottish crop production pathway. Where possible it is intended to work with industry to explore distillery co-product production environmental impact, with data from literature and appropriate databases intended to support and augment.

Simple processed non-crop additive

Simple processed non-crop additives identified are intended to be represented using information from key databases. The Global Feed LCA Institute (GFLI) database has been identified as the most

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appropriate source for this information, as it is a modern purpose made database specifically targeting and documenting the LCA impacts and consideration of feed-based ingredients. As fish oil is identified as one ingredient under this category, there is scope here for the model to be revisited later in the project and possibly augmented by utilising modelled Scottish produced fish oil as well. Data will be augmented by using information from literature as required.

Complex multi-ingredient additive

This aspect represents the hardest ingredients to model. While the ideal situation would be to treat each one as a complicated construct in the model, based on data from the manufacturer, the reality is that each individual multi-ingredient additive would be worthy of its own study. Furthermore, manufacturers are not necessarily willing to allow data access to details of their production process. However, there is agreements with the animal feed industry itself to provide CF estimations for their products. While these cannot be verified by this study, these will be used in lieu of primary data. Where possible this will be supported or challenged by data from the GFLI database. It should be noted at this point in the reporting, that although the complex multi-ingredient additives all show comparably high footprints in the industry reported data, this is reported per tonne of additive, not as a reflection on how much is used in the feed itself. Though an additive may have a high footprint, if its usage is low enough this still may only represent a small fraction of the overall feed environmental footprint. Until such time as relative quantities can be explored it cannot be determined how large a contribution any one ingredient may play.

Further considerations

While this study intends to explore the processing footprint of animal feed creation, discussion with industry have highlighted that to gain a true insight into the impacts of feed production, the estimation should not stop at per kg of feed produced, but rather per kg of meat or milk produced in livestock as a result. It has been pointed out that low quality feed might well have a lower CF per kg, but they will in turn show a lowered feed conversion ratio to the end product and this should be taken into account when making final conclusions of this study.

Also highlighted in the preliminary data provided by industry, there is different CFs associated with different feed mixes intended for different types of animals (calf rearing for meat, versus dairy cow feed). This is something else that should be explored, if possible, as different stages of life cycle and different purposes for the animals will logically require different dietary requirements.

Next Steps

The next intended step for this work package is to continue to work closely with the animal feed industry to gain data to allow for completion and running of the model to explore the relative footprint of a variety of feed mixes, and the influence of ingredient choice such as presence/absence of distillery co-products and soya products. It is also intended to work with the whisky industry to explore modelling of whisky processing as a whole, to represent the interlinked natures of the animal feed and the distilling industry. The modelling that has begun on the distillery co-products

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have by nature required the foundations of the whisky production model to be produced, resulting in a solid foundation for onward development.

Close work will continue with the C2-1 project to complete and further develop footprints for national crops and imported crops to feed into our models. Furthermore the GFLI database (GFLI, 2024) has been identified as the most suitable representation of secondary data for the model and purchase inquiries have been made with a view to completing before the beginning of Y3 to include in the final model development for both animal feed and the whisky industry.

Finally feed conversion ratios (and feed efficiency ratios) will be explored as suggested by industry. This will involve both liaising with industry for the reported ratios for the various feed produced by each company and research in literature for comparable ratios. Ultimate conclusions about environmental footprint will take these into account to offer the most accurate reflection of animal feed processing impact and contribution to food security.

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